

Space Exploration and Governance: What should we do to prepare for the era of space colonization?

Elbert Hubbard, an American writer, artist, and philosopher, once wrote: “One machine can do the work of fifty ordinary men. No machine can do the work of one extraordinary man.” Hubbard described himself as a socialist and anarchist, with beliefs in social and economic freedom, and a strong liking of other influential writers with similar beliefs, such as Leo Tolstoy and Walt Whitman. While Hubbard wasn’t fond of governmental organisations and governance in general, his opinions on the value of technology provide valuable insights on the importance of establishing robust governance systems over purely technological growth. Without these systems, space colonisation is doomed to fail; politically, ethically and socially.

In "Spacefarers" by Christopher Wanjek, Wanjek argues “Our renewed interest in human activity in space may actually lead to a permanent presence out there because it is being driven in part by “war,” but also by the promise of economic return.” Wanjek uses examples to support his claims, such as the Great Wall of China, which was “big and expensive” but extremely important for military purposes. Another example given to support Wanjek's point was the Apollo Program, a program whose purpose was militaristic. Although the United States invested about 318 Billion (2023) U.S. Dollars (according to the Tax Foundation), the National Space Society estimates a return on investment of 7 dollars for every dollar invested in the Apollo Program, as well as an overall return on investment of 40 dollars for every dollar spent on Space Development in the United States. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) continues to generate high economic output from activities, specifically their Moon to Mars activities, which a study found to have generated more than \$23.8 billion in total economic output in fiscal year 2023 alone, supporting an estimated 96,479 jobs nationwide. If humanity were to begin its space exploration and colonisation, it most probably would be for reasons mostly considered ethically immoral, such as economic gain, exploitation of resources and large scale war. An essential step in preventing this is

strengthening already existing accords, backing them up with more restrictions on all space-related activities.

But countries aren't the only ones in space anymore. One recent change to space exploration is the existence of private businesses operating in the space exploration sector, such as SpaceX and Virgin Galactic. The existence of these companies means that space is no longer exclusive to government agencies, but instead is available to anyone with enough funds and determination. NASA has also begun privatising its operations, opening the International Space Agency to commercial business in 2019. To find out what we must do to prepare for a new era of colonisation, we must use the past examples of colonisation and predict the future of Space Exploration and ways to handle the gradual privatisation of the sector. In a paper from Rachel B. Wickenheiser, an independent researcher from the University of Delaware, early American Colonisation is used to provide these same insights. Wickenheiser's main focus was the first English colony in North America, Jamestown Colony. Jamestown Colony was founded in 1607 by the Virginia Company, a for-profit company run by a president and seven-membered cabinet chosen by the King. After a "dismal failure," to become a profitable stock holding company, Virginia was made a royal colony in 1624 by King James I, and was held under British rule until the American revolution in 1776. The Virginia Company was also involved in several exploitation scandals, such as a mass poisoning in 1623, involving 200 native americans, and an attempted assassination of Pamunkey leader Opechancanough. The Smithsonian magazine discusses the significance of this event, deeming it one of the first war crimes on North American soil. As a preventative measure to ensure the safety of "Spaceworkers", the system must be made as transparent as possible, as should work externally from any government or for-profit organisation. "Spaceworkers" should have the ability to report their employers, just as any working citizen has the right to do on earth. This system should also be run internationally, ensuring the same universal rights apply to all "Spaceworkers", not just the ones from a certain country. Although Space most probably won't have a Native population to exploit, there will still be highly isolated workers in the first stages, forced to work with no way of returning before their scheduled returns.

There are also legal matters involved, can countries and private companies exploit space resources, or must they be used for the benefit of mankind? The 1967 Outer Space Treaty limits any space operations to peaceful purposes, banning any activity related to weapons of mass destruction, but doesn't solve the problem of space exploitation. Unlike the Outer Space Treaty, the Moon Agreement of 1979 restricts the exploitation of the moon's resources by a specific country, but as of January 2020, it is only ratified by 18 nations. In addition to the low number of endorsers, none of the nations have any human spaceflight capabilities, deeming the agreement obsolete.

The U.S. Commercial Space Launch Act of 2015 was signed into law by the U.S. President Barack Obama on the 25th of November 2015, allowing for U.S. Industries and individuals to "engage in the commercial exploration and exploitation of space resources". While asserting that by passing the act, the United States isn't claiming sovereignty over any celestial bodies, some question the implications it has on the aforementioned Outer Space Treaty. If private enterprises can exploit celestial bodies' resources while on international ground, what is stopping them from exploiting their workers on dangerous lunar mining missions, which under this new law are perfectly legal? How would unfair treatment of these workers be dealt with, and how would we deal with commercial business on unregulated international celestial bodies like the lunar surface? A number of countries are following suit, like Japan and the UAE, which have passed similar laws in the past few years, setting the precedent that the Outer Space Treaty isn't enforceable. In another controversial move, NASA tried to create lunar "exclusion zones" in 2011, where only NASA can land their aircraft, which both Russia and China have pointed out is a violation of the same treaty, and thus a violation of well established international law.

More recently, NASA's Artemis Accords have attempted to further enforce the Outer Space Treaty, with 54 signatories as of April 8th 2025. These Accords include the creation of safe zones to deconflict Space Activities, which NASA claims still respect the Outer Space Treaty as no country is claiming any of the land as theirs. Neither China or Russia have signed these accords, but other nations capable of orbital launches, such as; Japan, India, Israel, France and the UK, have signed this treaty, promising to uphold the

Outer Space Treaty and to make space a safer environment. This is a significant step toward establishing unanimously recognised international guidelines on Space Exploration, with the inclusion of the other spaceflight capable nations and U.S. adversaries, China and Russia. Many have called for the creation of this new treaty, indicating the weak and inconclusive laws have no way to be enforced, and haven't been adapted to recent technological advancements. In an article published by Taylor Wessing, an international law firm, Nick Storrs, a partner of the firm, argues that the Outer Space Treaty doesn't properly address major non-military uses of outer space with strong strategic purposes, such as Cyber-Warfare or Reconnaissance Satellites. Storrs also highlights the lack of governance structures, and the need for settler's rights while in space. In another article from Taylor Wessing, senior counsel Jo Joyce once again uses the history of colonisation to explain the risks of privatised space exploration. Joyce draws upon the colonisation of India, blaming the British and Dutch East India Companies for "massive waves of 19th Century European imperialism". Joyce brings attention in her article to the fact that no Nation State or private enterprise has seriously considered human's rights in outer space, which indicates the possibility of imperialism adjunct governance. This raises concerns over the true intentions of these private space companies, and how they would operate if allowed to continue with their activities. Will colonists be forced into indentured servitude, or will there be protections in place to stop it from happening? Protections that ensure the same rights we have on Earth.

Many artists and authors have attempted to recreate realistic space exploration and interplanetary colonies. One game that has managed to do so in multitudes of detail is Warhammer 40000, a miniature wargame produced by Games Workshop. The game was first introduced in September of 1987, and is currently on its 10th edition. In the "lore" or story of Warhammer 40000, there are several factions, each with different governance structures and rules. The imperium of man, the largest faction with over 1 million worlds, is described as an "authoritarian techno-feudal theocratic human empire". Although the game takes place in the 41st Millennium AD, the concept of an authoritarian theocratic society is already a part of many nations in present day Earth, such as the Holy See. The Imperium of Man is described as an empire on the brink of collapse, broken by war. It is ruled by a deathless emperor with unlimited psychic

power, requiring thousands of sacrifices daily to keep the empire running. The most insightful and relevant of all empires are the T'au, a relatively small empire of blue humanoid aliens with a mission to unite all other races under an ideology known as the "Greater Good". The "Greater Good" is a religion-philosophical principle based on utilitarian beliefs. The T'au empire shows how a unifying philosophy, like the "Greater Good", can help create social cohesion in a space colony. The T'au are focussed on unifying all intelligent races, focussing on diversity and inclusion, two principles that are essential for mankind to implement within their own colonies.

Warhammer wasn't the only highly successful interpretation of future space-based civilisations. Arguably the most famous space-related media franchise, Star Wars, is the 4th highest grossing media franchise of all time. Star Wars takes place at the core of a galactic conflict between the several republics and empires, most notably the Galactic Empire, which didn't take power through a violent takeover, but instead a "calculated dismantling" of the constitutional foundations imposed by the Jedi Council. In the prequel film Star Wars: Episode III – Revenge of the Sith, Chancellor Palpatine manipulates the Galactic Senate into using the clone troopers to exterminate the Jedi. Star Wars serves as a warning of the fragility of democratic institutions in the face of charismatic authoritarian figures, just as Warhammer's Imperium of Man, which shows how religion and fear overpower governance. Both these universes demonstrate the importance of ethical and inclusive governance, and how a seemingly stable society can fail without proper ethical governance and political accountability.

To conclude this essay, it is important to highlight that Outer Space and all celestial bodies are under the Outer Space Treaty ownership of the whole of mankind. As mankind, we cannot allow one nation or enterprise to solely control humanity's access to outer space. Fiction warns us that absolute power leads to oppression and instability, and that a fair society must be inclusive and unifying, working towards a cause, not selfish gain. We must also build frameworks that prioritize human rights and accountability before colonisation and exploration begins, ones rooted in benefiting all of mankind, not just one race or group. History has shown that autocracies don't tend to last, but our future in space isn't just another territory, it is a necessary step toward

technological advancement and our species' survival. As we prepare to leave Earth behind, we must remember where we came from, our humanity, and how to maintain such values. Governance in space will not be a question of power alone, but of who we choose to become when no one is watching.

(Word Count: 1999/2000)

Works Cited

- Bardan, Roxana. "New Report Shows NASA's \$75.6 Billion Boost to US Economy." *NASA*, 24 Oct. 2024,
<https://www.nasa.gov/news-release/new-report-shows-nasas-75-6-billion-boost-to-us-economy/>.
- Corinna-Tri. "The Ethics of Space Exploration." *Trilateral Research*, 19 Nov. 2020,
<https://trilateralresearch.com/emerging-technology/the-ethics-of-space-exploration>.
- Daines, Gary. *Artemis Accords - NASA*. NASA, 2023.
- "Greater Good." *Warhammer 40k Wiki*, Fandom, Inc.,
https://warhammer40k.fandom.com/wiki/Greater_Good. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.
- Higgs, Milly. "Space Race and the Cost of Industrial Policy." *Tax Foundation*, 24 July 2024,
<https://taxfoundation.org/blog/apollo-moon-space-race-industrial-policy-cost/>.
- Hubbard, Elbert. *A Thousand & One Epigrams: And, the Roycroft Shop: A History*. 1973.
- "Imperium of Man." *Warhammer 40k Wiki*, Fandom, Inc.,
https://warhammer40k.fandom.com/wiki/Imperium_of_Man. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.
- "No Title." *Nss.org*,
<https://nss.org/settlement/nasa/spaceresvol4/newspace3.html>. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.

Peters, Declan. "The Legal Grey Area of Mining the Moon." *Legal Cheek*, 29 May 2024,
<https://www.legalcheek.com/lc-journal-posts/the-sticky-legal-issues-with-mining-the-moon/>.

"The Virginia Company of London - Historic Jamestowne Part of Colonial National Historical Park (U.s. National Park Service)." *Nps.gov*,
<https://www.nps.gov/jame/learn/historyculture/the-virginia-company-of-london.htm>. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.

Wanjek, Christopher. *Spacefarers: How Humans Will Settle the Moon, Mars, and Beyond*. Harvard University Press, 2020.

Wickenheiser, Rachel B. "Profits over People: The Dangers of Privatizing Space Colonization." *Futures*, vol. 169, no. 103592, 2025, p. 103592,
doi:10.1016/j.futures.2025.103592.

Wikipedia contributors. "Anarchism." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 15 Apr. 2025,
<https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Anarchism&oldid=1285718051>.

---. "Colonization of the Moon." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 6 Mar. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Colonization_of_the_Moon&oldid=1279056652.

---. "Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act of 2015." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 23 June 2024,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Commercial_Space_Launch_Competitiveness_Act_of_2015&oldid=1230564587.

---. "Elbert Hubbard." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 20 Apr. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Elbert_Hubbard&oldid=1286496264.

---. "Galactic Empire (Star Wars)." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 24 Apr. 2025,
[https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Galactic_Empire_\(Star_Wars\)&oldid=1287096198](https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Galactic_Empire_(Star_Wars)&oldid=1287096198).

---. "List of Highest-Grossing Media Franchises." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 17 Apr. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=List_of_highest-grossing_media_franchises&oldid=1286010583.

---. "Politics of Vatican City." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 24 Apr. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Politics_of_Vatican_City&oldid=1287175853.

---. "Spaceflight." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 22 Apr. 2025,
<https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Spaceflight&oldid=1286907677>.

---. "Star Wars." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 21 Apr. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Star_Wars&oldid=1286784564.

---. "Warhammer 40,000." *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*, 17 Apr. 2025,
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Warhammer_40,000&oldid=1286124128.

Oup.com, <https://academic.oup.com/function/article/4/1/zqac073/6987091>.
Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.

Smithsonianmag.com,
<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/was-the-1623-poisoning-of-200-native-americans-the-continent's-first-war-crime-180982202/>.
Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.

Taylorwessing.com,

<https://www.taylorwessing.com/en/interface/2024/the-space-race/outer-space-needs-a-new-treaty>. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.

Taylorwessing.com,

<https://www.taylorwessing.com/en/interface/2022/space-law/human-rights-in-space>. Accessed 25 Apr. 2025.